

THE EFFECT OF BIOECONOMY ON FOOD SECURITY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Food is an important aspect of cultural heritage for national identity, which has led to its recognition as a fundamental human right. It links individuals and places, bringing friends and family together. It is impossible to overestimate its effects on human and economic development, as well as its psychological implications for mood. However, achieving food security in the face of a growing population while maintaining a constant supply of natural resources is difficult, particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria. This confirms Malthus's population theory, which states that the human population expands exponentially while food grows arithmetically. Nevertheless, the theory has failed to consider how agricultural innovation and improved technological know-how could address the earth's law of decreasing returns. The Nigerian government has used a novel strategy called Bioeconomy in an effort to attain food security. A bioeconomy is an economy that produces food, feed, medicines, and energy from waste materials and biological resources found in the soil and ocean. This study investigates the effect of bioeconomy on food security, with bioeconomy measured by a value-added approach and food security proxied using a food production index that reflects food availability.

Secondary data from 1980 to 2020 were used, collected from World Bank Development Indicators (WDI, 2024) and the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (CBN, 2024). This study used the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) approach. It discovered that the bioeconomy has a positive but insignificant ($p > 0.05$, $t = 2.089$) relationship with food security in Nigeria. The findings corroborate the a priori expectation that the bioeconomy contributes to food security. The study indicates that the bioeconomy promotes food security. According to the study, food security is enhanced by bioeconomy. The study recommends that for the government to meet the demands of the growing population and achieve sustainable development, the government should ensure broad biotechnological knowledge.

Keywords: *Bioeconomy, Mood, Sustainable Development, Food Security.*

1.0 Introduction

Nigeria as a country is Africa's most populous country from time immemorial and it faces significant challenges in ensuring food security. Economic shocks, extreme weather, population growth, and conflict are some of the causes of food insecurity (FSIN and Global Network Against Food Crises, 2023). Approximately 2.4 billion people, or 29.6% of the global population, experienced moderate to severe food insecurity in 2022. The largest concentration of food-insecure people was found in Africa (FAO, IFAD, WFP, and WHO, 2023; Hegazi and Seyuba, 2024). While Nigeria's population has also increased to about 232,679,478 people which is about 2.85 % of the world's population (Worldometer, 2024). The Malthus theory of population (1978), which holds that while natural resources for food production are growing arithmetically, the world population is growing geometrically, was supported by the country's reliance on traditional agricultural practices and the effects of climate change, which made food insecurity problems worse. The rise in the global population led to the development of Malthus's theory (Ajayi and Akinbobola, 2022). The theory has been criticized for neglecting the possibility of the intervention of technology to meet the increase in demand for food as a result of the increase in population.

Moreover, food is the most important of all the basic needs of humans (Magrabi, 1991). Food security is the same as achieving the sustainable development goal 2 (SDG2) of zero hunger by 2030 (Malec *et al.*, 2024). Ensuring access to food and its availability is vital for enhancing human development and potential, as it plays a critical role in strengthening human capabilities (Abdi *et al.* 2024). According to Ajayi and Akinbobola (2020), food security is a situation in which people have constant access to adequate, safe, and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and preferences for an active and healthy lifestyle. Food security is a critical prerequisite for any population's welfare and can threaten its existence if not managed properly (Martínez-Jaramillo *et al.*, 2019).

To achieve food security, scholars and policymakers have emphasized that government must adopt a new bio-economy approach. The bioeconomy, which uses biological resources for sustainable development, offers potential solutions to these challenges and helps to improve the quality of life (Okunlola *et al.*, 2022). It includes areas such as sustainable agriculture, biotechnology, and renewable resources (Dedeurwaerdere *et al.*, 2012). In the context of food security, bio-economy strategies aim to enhance agricultural productivity, reduce waste, and develop resilient food systems (OECD, 2009). Nigeria has initiated various bioeconomic strategies to address food security challenges which can be explained in the following dimensions. Firstly, the bio-technological Innovations which is the development of genetically modified crops with enhanced resistance to pests and diseases, and improved nutritional content. Examples include drought-resistant maize and nutrient-enriched cassava (Akintoye *et al.*, 2019).

Secondly, sustainable Agricultural Practices include the adoption of practices such as organic farming, integrated pest management, and the use of biofertilizers. These methods aim to improve soil health and reduce environmental impact (Ogunlela *et al.*, 2013). The third aspect is Renewable Resources and Waste Management which involves the utilization of agricultural by-products and waste for energy production and soil enhancement. This includes the

production of biogas from organic waste excreted from animals like chickens or cows and crop residues as bio-based materials for planting crops (Iwegbue *et al.*, 2015). Lastly, the Implementation of government policies and programs to support bioeconomic development, such as subsidies for biotechnology research and investment in agricultural infrastructure (NABDA, 2021) go a long way toward higher production and food security.

Moreover, achieving food security is not only a matter of ensuring that people have enough food to eat but also encompasses the psychological aspects of food availability. It is the mindset of an average individual that gives assurance that food is available when I want to eat, and I don't have to struggle for it. The relationship between food security and mental health is complex and multifaceted, affecting individuals' stress levels, emotional well-being, and overall quality of life of individuals. Stress and anxiety are some of the psychological factors that can be caused by food insecurity. It can lead to chronic stress as a result of uncertainty about where the next meal will come from. If this type of anxiety persists it can impair mental health and exacerbate other stress-related conditions (Coleman-Jensen *et al.*, 2023). Persistent food insecurity can negatively affect cognitive function and academic performance, particularly in children. Nutritional deficiencies can impair brain development and cognitive abilities, leading to poor academic outcomes and increased negative behavioral issues (Walker *et al.*, 2022). Thereby turning the future generations into non-entity. Furthermore, food security is essential for increasing worker earnings, reducing conflict and violence, and increasing labor productivity (Brinkman and Hendrix, 2011; Malec *et al.*, 2024). Food security is therefore essential to reducing poverty and advancing national development as a whole.

Therefore, a country that is well meaning would endeavor to make food a priority by enhancing and supporting organizations and projects like bioeconomy to improve food availability in the country. Despite, the introduction and adoption of bioeconomy through biotechnological processes, the literature has not provided empirical evidence of the effect of bioeconomy on food security. It is necessary to examine the relationship between bioeconomy and food security in Nigeria, in order to understand the psychological and economic implications of food security. Hence, this study examines the effect of bioeconomy on food security in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

2.2 Determinant of Food Security

Table 1 shows the factors that determine the four dimensions of food security.

Determinant	Description	Factors
1. Food Availability	the actual presence of enough food in a given location, either through imports, local production, or food aid.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agricultural productivity - Infrastructure (roads, storage) - Climate conditions - Trade policies
2. Food Access	the capacity of people or households to acquire enough food by trading, buying, or producing food for subsistence.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Household income - Food prices - Social safety nets - Market access
3. Food Utilization	the right use of food for nutritional well-being, encompassing food quality, safety, and nutrient metabolism.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutritional knowledge - Water and sanitation - Health services - Food diversity
4. Stability	the continuity of food accessibility and availability over time, guaranteeing that food is available in both temporary and permanent circumstances.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic stability - Climate variability - Conflict and political stability - Food price volatility
5. Political and Economic Stability	The political and economic landscape shapes social welfare initiatives, resource distribution, and policy decisions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government policies - International trade agreements - Political conflicts - Economic growth and inflation
6. Social Factors	Food distribution, availability, and dietary preferences are influenced by social structures and cultural behaviors which are the social factors.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gender roles - Cultural dietary preferences - Social inequality - Household decision-making dynamics
7. Environmental Factors	The effects of environmental factors on food systems' long-term sustainability, food production, and food distribution.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Land quality and degradation - Water resources - Climate change - Biodiversity
8. Technological Factors	The potential of technology to enhance food production, delivery, and storage systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agricultural innovations - Food preservation methods - Supply chain technology - Biotechnology
9. Infrastructure	Organizational and physical frameworks that facilitate the effective production, delivery, and storage of food.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transportation networks - Storage facilities - Market infrastructure - Communication systems
10. Global Factors	the impact of international relations, trade laws, and world markets on food security.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - International trade policies - Foreign aid - Global food prices - Import/export restrictions

Source: Authors' compilation, 2024

2.3 Empirical Review on Food Security

Table 2 shows the empirical literature on food security

S/N	AUTHOR (S)	TITLE	METHODOLOGY	FINDINGS
1.	Martínez-Jaramillo <i>et al.</i> , (2019)	The effects of biofuels on food security: A system dynamics approach for the Colombian case	system dynamics model	It discovered that by 2030, Colombia's acreage devoted to agriculture would have decreased as a result of the use of biofuels. This ultimately causes the amount of food to drop and the price of food to rise.
2.	Subramaniam <i>et al.</i> , (2019)	1 THE IMPACT OF BIOFUELS ON FOOD SECURITY IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES	Generalized Method of Moments (GMM)	Biofuels negatively affect food security in poor nations.
3.	Subramaniam <i>et al.</i> , (2020)	2 BIOFUELS, ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY, AND FOOD SECURITY: A REVIEW OF 51 COUNTRIES	Dynamic Generalized Method of Moments	It demonstrates that there is a positive and substantial influence on food security from the interaction between biofuels and environmental quality. This suggests. Thus, a large increase in the production and use of biofuels may help to maintain environmental quality and increase food security.
4.	2.1 Ahmed (2020)	3 THE EFFECT OF BIOFUEL CROPS CULTIVATION ON FOOD PRICES STABILITY AND FOOD SECURITY REVIEW.	Review	A shift in the use of agricultural land from growing food crops to growing oilseeds for the production of biofuel results in food shortages and rising prices because basic crop production is declining and demand for these crops, which are primarily used for food, is rising. These countries export food crops like wheat, barley, and rice.
5.	Brinkman <i>et al.</i> , (2020)	The distribution of food security impacts of biofuels, a Ghana case study	Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) Mode	The findings indicate that the biofuel mandate's negative effects on food prices and import dependency have the most implications on food security. However, in comparison to the expected effects of Ghana's economic expansion on food security until 2030, the estimated impacts of the biofuel requirement on food security are negligible.

6.	Osuji et al., (2020)	Implications of Macro-Economic Variables for National Food Security In Nigeria	Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL)	Food security was significantly impacted by the interest rate, inflation, government spending, and money supply, according to the results of long- and short-term associations.
7.	Gershon and Mbajekwe, (2020)	Nexus of Climate Change and Agricultural Production In Nigeria	Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL)	The results showed that although there is no long-term correlation between crop production and climate change, there is one between animal productivity and climate change.
9.	Muhammed and Iliyasu (2021)	4 FOOD IMPORT DEMAND AND DOMESTIC FOOD PRODUCTION IN NIGERIA	<i>Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL)</i>	Research indicates that as local food production rises, the need for imported food declines in the near term, indicating its significance as a substitute in the economy. The rising demand for imported food in Nigeria is also largely influenced by trade openness, income, and import prices.
10.	Akinbobola and Ajayi (2023)	Bioeconomy and Food Security (SDG 2): Case Study of Nigeria	Content analysis	It discovers that bioeconomy aids food security in Nigeria.
11.	Obilor and Awogub (2023)	5 URBANIZATION AND FOOD PRODUCTION IN OWERRI NORTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, NIGERIA	descriptive statistics	According to the report, even while food imports and bills have historically accounted for a larger percentage of food than exports, this has contributed to a rise in food insecurity and a decline in Nigeria's food affordability, quality, and safety standards.
12.	Wudil et al. (2023)	6 HOUSEHOLDS FOOD SECURITY DETERMINANTS AMONG THE BENEFICIARIES AND NON-BENEFICIARIES RICE FARMERS OF THE KANO RIVER IRRIGATION PROJECT IN NIGERIA.	A semi-structured questionnaire	The results also showed that the recipients' levels of food insecurity are, respectively, 11% and 4%. Conversely, the depth and severity of food insecurity among non-beneficiaries were 17 and 8%, respectively.
13.	Verter (2019)	Food Security and Trade in Food Products in Nigeria 7	Descriptive Approaches	The report also shows that Nigeria has had extreme food insecurity due to several factors, including a lack of safety net programs, population expansion, poverty, corruption, and a lack of proper government support for farmers.

14.	Obayelu <i>et al.</i> , (2024)	Assessment of Agricultural Trade Flow and Food Security Status: Evidence from Nigeria	Descriptive analysis	The results showed that while the percentage of food imports and food bills was larger than the percentage of exports over time, this led to a rise in food insecurity and a decline in Nigeria's food affordability, quality, and safety conditions. The exchange of agricultural products is crucial to ensuring food security.
15.	Gana <i>et al.</i> , (2024)	The Interplay Between Climate Change And Food Security In Nigeria: Challenges And Opportunities	Thematic approach	The results show that Nigeria is dealing with rising temperatures, unpredictable rainfall patterns, droughts, floods, and desertification. These issues are making the country more vulnerable to food insecurity and producing lower agricultural yields for the millions of people who depend on it.
16.	He <i>et al.</i> (2024)	the impact of green economic growth and renewable energy on food security in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA).	GMM.	The results show that renewable energy and green economic growth have a favorable and significant impact on food security, albeit unevenly across SSA subregions. However, because of its emissions, industrialization has a major impact on food security.
17.	Hegazi and Seyuba (2024)	Gender, livelihood diversification, and food security: Insights from rural communities in Zambia	the descriptive and qualitative approach	The study concludes that food security for households led by women is enhanced by on-farm diversity. The study also discovers that, in comparison to off-farm diversification, on-farm diversification was more successful in enhancing the food security experiences of families led by women.
18.	Malec <i>et al.</i> , (2024)	Impact of investments in agricultural innovation on food security in sub-Saharan Africa	Two-system GMM	The results demonstrate how investments in agricultural innovation significantly boost food security by raising food productivity. The results also show that while the investments worsen the issue of food insecurity in Central Africa, they are more successful in improving food security in the sub-regions of Eastern, Southern, and Western Africa.

19.	Abdi et al. (2024)	Enhancing food security in sub-Saharan Africa: Investigating the role of environmental degradation, food prices, and institutional quality	panel autoregressive distributed lag	Long-term and short-term increases in agricultural land contribute to improved food security, according to the results of the pooled mean group (PMG) models. Similarly, increased food demand is driven by population growth, rising per capita income, and capital formation, all of which improve the state of food security.
20.	Enilolobo et al. (2021)	Determinants of Food Security in Nigeria	autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL)	The study found that domestic capital had a substantial positive impact on food security and bank lending only had a significant positive impact on food security in Nigeria.

Source: Authors' Compilation, 2024

3.0 Psychological and Economical Importance/Implication of Food Security

3.1 Economic Implication/Importance of Food Security

Food is not only essential for survival but also a critical driver of economic activity across the globe. From agriculture to retail, the food industry creates jobs, supports livelihoods, and fuels national economies. The economic significance of food spans multiple dimensions, including its role in agriculture, trade, employment, and public health among others. The following are some of the importance/implications of food security.

a) **Rural Development:** In agrarian economies, food production supports rural communities by providing income, employment, and business opportunities. When agriculture thrives, it can drive infrastructure development, educational opportunities, and financial services in rural areas (Tersoo 2014; Osabohien, et al 2019).

b) **Employment creation:** Food production is essential to global employment. The agricultural sector alone employs more than 26% of the global workforce, with rural areas heavily dependent on farming for income (FAO, 2023). In countries like the United States, the food services industry employs over 15 million people, making up more than 10% of the total workforce (Landry et al., 2022; *Noguchi, 2020*). This sector's resilience was evident in its post-pandemic recovery, underscoring its critical role in national economies (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2023; Pop et al., 2024). The labor implications of food production are multifaceted which include agricultural employment, and urban employment in the food sector.

c) **GDP Contribution:** In many countries, food production and agriculture contribute significantly to the GDP. For example, agriculture contributes about 4% to global GDP, though this share is higher in developing countries like India and Nigeria, where it accounts for over 15% of GDP.

d) **Technological Innovation:** The demand for more food due to population growth stimulates technological advancements in agricultural production. Innovations such as precision agriculture, biotechnology, and mechanization enhance productivity, reduce costs, and increase efficiency. Technological innovations in the food industry, particularly in agriculture, are creating new economic opportunities. The market for alternative proteins, including plant-based and cultured meats, was valued at \$10.3 billion in 2022 and is expected to grow substantially, driven by consumer demand for healthier and more sustainable options (McKinsey & Company, 2024). These advancements can significantly improve the economy by reducing food prices and making resources more sustainable. Moreover, technological advancements in agriculture, such as precision farming, genetically modified crops, and irrigation systems, have enhanced food production efficiency. These innovations not only help meet the growing food demand but also reduce production costs and create new economic opportunities for agribusinesses.

e) **Environmental Sustainability:** There is a growing movement towards sustainable food systems, which aim to balance the economic, social, and environmental aspects of food production. By adopting more sustainable agricultural practices, such as regenerative farming and reducing food waste, economies can benefit from healthier ecosystems and reduced costs associated with environmental damage.

f) **Culinary Tourism and Local Economies:** Food is increasingly recognized as a cultural asset that drives tourism. Culinary tourism, which includes food festivals, local cuisines, and farm-to-table experiences, contributed over \$150 billion globally in 2021 (Statista, 2022). This form of tourism attracts millions of tourists, bolstering local economies and creating jobs in hospitality and food services.

g) **Inflation:** Rising food prices significantly impact global economies, often driving inflation. In 2023, food price inflation became a major factor in overall inflation, as supply chain disruptions and climate events (such as droughts and floods) caused shortages and price hikes (World Bank, 2023). The FAO Food Price Index shows that food price volatility can lead to economic instability, particularly in low-income countries where a larger share of household income is spent on food (FAO, 2023). This volatility can affect both the economic growth and political stability of these nations.

h) **Trade and Global Markets:** Food exports and imports play a critical role in international trade. In 2022, global food exports were valued at over \$1.5 trillion, with countries like the United States, Brazil, and the European Union being the largest exporters (OECD, 2022). This trade not only supports domestic economies but also ensures global food security by enabling countries with limited agricultural capacity to access essential foodstuffs. Recent disruptions in the food supply chain, due to the pandemic and conflicts like the Ukraine-Russia war, have highlighted the interconnectedness of global food markets and their impact on economic stability (Benton, 2017, FAO, 2023).

3.2 Psychological Importance/Implication of Food

Food is significant to our livelihood as individuals and as a community. Food is an essential part of sustainability for individuals and nations. Food is part of the basic need for human survival according to Maslow's (1954) hierarchy of needs, food, and water, are part of the first biological basic needs that an individual requires to survive. These needs according to Maslow's hierarchy of needs must be achieved before moving to the next hierarchy of

needs. Therefore, food is a crucial necessity for survival. The following are some of the highlighted psychological importance of food.

- a) **Food enhances mood and regulates emotions:** Food also enhances mood through neurotransmitter modulation (Shen *et al.*, 2024). Neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine are responsible for the balancing of our mood, sleep, and cognitive functioning. The human brain relies on the production of these neurotransmitters which emanate from the food we eat. These neurotransmitters send signals between brain cells and regulate the functioning of the central nervous system. Studies have shown that serotonin which is the ‘feel-good’ neurotransmitter is essential for reducing anxiety and depression (Sandua, 2024). Interestingly, an essential part of the serotonin is produced in the gut, where the food eaten plays a crucial role. For instance, diets high in omega-3 fatty acids and antioxidants such as fatty fish produce serotonin which is linked to lower rates of depression (Jacka *et al.*, 2017). Other food we eat also promotes healthy vital nutrients to synthesize the neurotransmitters such as dopamine and norepinephrine. Food like legumes, vegetables, grains, and carbohydrates supply energy for the brain functioning and help to stabilize sugar levels which helps to reduce mood swings.
- b) **Food also gives a form of comfort and relief stress:** Aside from the fact that food produces neurotransmitters that relieve stress, many people use food as a form of coping mechanism during stress, leading to temporary emotional relief and comfort but potentially negative long-term effects on mental health, when they overeat, leading to obesity or eating disorder (Shen *et al.*, 2024).
- c) **Body Image and Self-esteem:** Food helps in boosting the self-esteem of individuals, especially Africans where being fat is appreciated. There is a cultural belief that a healthy look of a woman’s fertility is seen in how fat she looks, especially for an Annang bride in Nigeria. There is a culture of keeping the young bride in a fattening room where she would be fed with food that would enhance her skin and make her fat. Being fat is beauty for Africans, which also helps to improve the self-esteem and Image of the family members receiving and giving the bride. The relationship between food, body image, and self-esteem is significant, especially in young adults, with diet culture contributing to it.
- d) **Cultural Identity and Food Practices:** Food is central to cultural identity, and globalization can influence traditional food practices and perceptions, impacting psychological well-being (Boutaud *et al.*, 2016). Food serves as a huge cultural significance, especially in Africa. Africa sees food as a form of affluence and abundance. Food is used as an exchange of gifts and also part of the bride price that is demanded of the groom’s relative. They are asked to bring tubers of yam, bags of rice and beans, gallons of palm oil and vegetable oil, and a live goat, cow, or chicken among many other gift items are required as bride price (Chae *et al.*, 2021). Food is also served to guests as a form of appreciation for coming to an event. Likewise from the Annang culture, the act of fattening the bride boosts the pride or esteem of the bride and the bride’s parent. This cultural practice is sending a signal to the husband that their daughter must not be starved or maltreated (Brink, 1995).
- e) **Nutritional Psychiatry:** is an emerging field that emphasizes the link between diet and mental health, this field has shown that dietary improvements can significantly affect psychological conditions like depression and anxiety in individuals (Jacka *et al.*, 2017). The lack of food can cause anxiety, leading to low blood sugar and nutrient deficiencies which can truncate the neurotransmitter balance. Lack of food can also cause dehydration because thirst

sometimes acts as hunger, thereby causing dehydration and exacerbating anxiety (Shen *et al.*, 2024).

4.0 Methodology

4.1 Theoretical Framework

This study is based on the Malthus theory of population (1798) which is also referred to as the food availability theory and is based on two premises population expands exponentially and food grows arithmetically. The food availability approach is the oldest approach of food security theory. The theory explains that “the power of the earth to produce subsistence for humans is lower than the power of population which increases over time”. This theory emphasizes that for equilibrium to be maintained between population and food the growth rate of food availability should not be lower than the growth rate of the population. The fast rate of population expansion and declining agricultural returns led to the development of the Malthusian population theory.

However, Malthus's theory of population has been criticized for his notion that the supply of food increases arithmetically is based on the law of diminishing returns, neglecting. The potential for advancements in agricultural technology and knowledge that could help humanity overcome the law of diminishing returns. This theory is further supported by Mill's theory (1848) that a lack of technical improvement in agriculture and an increase in population growth rate with a low capital accumulation rate will make a profit at its minimum and the economy at a stationary state. Mill's theory, therefore, encouraged technological improvements to increase the productivity of land which is a standard cardinal principle for economic development in underdeveloped countries. This has led to technological advancement and improvement in agriculture which enable the adoption of bioeconomy. Bioeconomy is driven by biotechnological innovations and genetic engineering which improves crop yields, and decrease the effect of pests. Efficient food production and less vulnerability to both environmental and economic shocks could be achieved via these technologies. Biotechnology and genetic engineering are identified as the mechanisms through which bioeconomy improves food security.

Fundamentally, food Security is described as the function of both the quantity and quality of food required. Quantity in terms of the amount of food available, accessibility, and quality in terms of food safety and nutritious value (Larbode *et al.*, 2016). Bioeconomy can therefore be captured as a factor that determines both the quantity and the quality of food. Food security is primarily from the individual level to the national or country level. Food security can therefore be written as a function of quality and quantity.

$$FS = f(Quality, Quantity) \tag{1}$$

4.2 Model specification

From equation (1), both quantity and quality could be defined as a function of factors that are not in control of the individuals, which can be economic, social, physical, and environmental

factors (Laborde *et al.*, 2013; Laborde *et al.*, 2016). Quality is the quality of food and quantity is the quantity of food.

From equation (1) quantity of food can be written as:

$$\text{Quantity of food} = f(\text{fim}, \text{pop}, \text{y}, \text{rex}) \quad (2)$$

Also, from equation (1) the quality of food can be written as:

$$\text{Quality of food} = f(\text{inf}, \text{unem}) \quad (3)$$

A high inflation rate will reduce the purchasing power of an individual in the market goods thereby demanding goods that may not satisfy the needs of the individual. Unemployment also reduces the ability of an individual to consume goods with high quality but will rather consume the food that he/she can buy.

Substituting equations (2) and (3) into (1), we have:

$$FS = f(\text{fim}, \text{pop}, \text{y}, \text{rex}, \text{inf}, \text{unem}) \quad (4)$$

However, from the literature, bioeconomy has been identified as the solution to food insecurity which negates Malthus's theory of population that neglects the possibility of technological knowledge and invention in agriculture. Other factors include population, income, real exchange rate, and inflation. Following the studies by Tonukari & Omotor (2010), Qaim and Virchow (2011), Meerman and Aphane, 2012; Larbode *et al.*, (2013), Adom (2014), Oke (2015), Laborde *et al.*, (2016), Ajayi and Akinbobola, (2020) among others, food security model can therefore be written as follows:

$$FS = f(\text{fim}, \text{pop}, \text{y}, \text{rex}, \text{inf}, \text{unem}, \text{bioe}) \quad (5)$$

Implicitly, equation (5) is given as:

$$FS = \text{fim}^\delta \text{pop}^\sigma \text{unem}^\eta \text{y}^\omega \text{bioe}^\beta \text{inf}^\rho \text{rex}^\partial \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) in its linear and Generalized Method of Moment form can be written as:

$$FS_t = \alpha FS_{t-1} + \delta \text{fim}_t + \sigma \text{pop}_t + \eta \text{unem}_t + \omega \text{y}_t + \beta \text{bioe}_t + \rho \text{inf}_t + \partial \text{rex}_t + \mu_t \quad (7)$$

Following a study by Applanaidu and Baharudin (2014) food security is measured using the log of food production index. FS is food security, POP is the population growth rate, UNEM, is the log of the unemployment rate, Y is the per capita income, BIOE is bioeconomy, REX is real exchange rate, t is time, FIM is food import, INF is the inflation rate, μ is the error term, are coefficients of explanatory variables. A priori expectation is that per capita income, food import, and bioeconomy will have a direct relationship with food security while unemployment, real exchange rate, inflation, and population growth will have an inverse relationship with food security. Mathematically, from equation (7), the a priori expectation is given as:

$$\delta > 0; \omega > 0; \beta > 0; \alpha > 0; \rho > 0; \eta < 0, \sigma < 0; \partial < 0.$$

4.2.1 Hypothesis Test

H₀: Bioeconomy through biotechnological application does not improve food security in Nigeria.

H₁: Bioeconomy through biotechnological application improves food security in Nigeria.

4.2 Data

The variables used in this study were sourced from both World Bank Development Indicators (WDI) and the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistic Bulletin (CBN). The data covered the period from 1980 to 2020. Table 3 below shows the description, measurement, and sources of data on variables.

Variables	Description	Measurement	Sources
Bioeconomy	Bioeconomy is an economy in which biotechnology stimulates economic outputs to a large extent.	It is measured by an index of value-added, export and investment (SAT-BBE Consortium, 2013; Bracco & Flamming, 2018). Value-added (VA) of bioeconomy related sectors i.e palm oil, rubber, wood products, food products, biodiesel. Export (E) is the value of export of all biobased products (excluding minerals such as oil and coal) to GDP. Investment (I) is the proportion of GDP in bioeconomy sector.	CBN (2023)
Food security	Food security is a situation in which food is available, accessible, utilized and stable for all people at the same time and at all times.	Food Production Index (FPI) The food Production Index is food crops that are edible and contain nutrients. It is calculated by dividing the aggregate given for a year by the average aggregate for the base year.	WDI (2023)
Population growth	This is the measure of the increase in the number of individuals in a population.	The annual growth rate of the population.	WDI (2023)
Unemployment	Unemployment is the share of the labour force that lacks jobs and is actively employable.	Unemployment rate	WDI (2023)
Per capita income	This is income earned per person.	This is GDP divided by Mid-Year Population	WDI (2023)
Real exchange rate	A real effective exchange rate is a measure of the value of a currency against a weighted average of several foreign currencies.	It is measured as a nominal effective exchange rate divided by a price deflator.	WDI (2023)
Food import	It covers food and live animals, beverages, tobacco, animals and vegetable oil, oilseeds, nuts oil and kernels oil (WDI, 2019).	It is measured as a percentage of merchandise imports.	WDI (2023)
Inflation	The inflation rate is the persistent increase in the level of price of goods and services in a country.	Inflation rate	WDI (2023)

Source: Authors' compilation, 2024

4.3 Technique of Analysis

The effect of the bioeconomy on food security in Nigeria is investigated using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM), which was created by Hansen in 1982. This is justified because the simultaneity and endogeneity issues among the variables in the model cause the inclusion of the lagged dependent variable among the independent variables to provide biased and inconsistent estimates when using OLS to estimate the model. The suitability of the tools employed has a significant impact on the accuracy of the GMM estimates. Theoretically, a variable must be unrelated to the residual term yet connected to explanatory factors to be employed as an instrument. These tools are employed to eliminate any potential correlation between the error term and the explanatory variables. According to the literature, one tool that can be employed is the lag of explanatory variables. It is assumed that past values of variables are uncorrelated with error term while using lag values of explanatory variables as instruments (Wooldridge, 2001). For the models, the sargan test value should be nearer one, indicating that the instrument is valid and the null hypothesis can be accepted. In order to validate and support the employment of the GMM model, it is also crucial to check for serial correlation of the residual. Using the Arellano and Bond serial correlation AR (1) and AR (2) tests, which were created by Arellano and Bond (1991), the study adheres to the literature on GMM. Specifically, the AR (1) and AR (2) tests are performed to determine whether the model has first-order and second-order.

5.0 INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

5.1 Descriptive Analysis

This section focuses on descriptive analyses and it contains the measures of central tendency (which include mean and median), measures of variation, and other statistical characteristics of the variables. It is essential to estimate the descriptive statistics before analysing time series data to avoid some problems that might arise in empirical analysis.

From Table 5, it is observed that the unemployment rate (UNEM), per capita income (Y), inflation (INF), real exchange rate (REX), and population growth (POP) were positively skewed, which indicates that they have long right tails. By implication, their mean is greater than their median, and their median greater than their mode. Bioeconomy (BIOE), food import (FIM), and food security (FS) are negatively skewed, which indicates they have long left tails. This explains that their mean is less than their median and their median is less than their mode.

The descriptive statistics also report kurtosis. The Kurtosis measures the peakness or flatness of the distribution of the series. If the Kurtosis is 3, it is mesokurtic, if the kurtosis is greater than 3, the distribution is peaked or leptokurtic relative to the normal and if the kurtosis is less than three, the distribution is flat or turned platykurtic relative to normal. From Table, food security (FS), bioeconomy (BIOE), real exchange rate (REX), per capita income (Y,) and

inflation rate (INF) were flat or less than 3, indicating that the series is platykurtic. This implies that these series have thinner tails than a normal distribution which results in few extreme positive or negative values. Unemployment (UNEM), food import (FIM) and population growth (POP) peaked or leptokurtic because their values were greater than 3. This implies that these series have flatter tails than normal distribution which result in extreme positive or negative values.

Lastly, the Table shows the Jarque-Bera test statistic. The Jarque-Bera is used to test for normality in the distribution of the series. The test statistic also measures the difference of the skewness and kurtosis of the series with those with normal distribution. From Table 5 education food security (FS), bioeconomy (BIOE), per capita income (Y), real exchange rate (REX), inflation(INF), and population growth rate (POP), do not have a normal distribution while, food import (FIM) and unemployment rate (UNEM) are normally distributed.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics

Variable	FS	UNEM	BIOE	Y	INF	FIM	REX	POP
Mean	4.2146	1.407	6.637	12.411	2.673	2.797	4.815	0.950
Median	4.3484	1.374	6.807	12.293	2.502	2.880	4.610	0.950
Maximum	4.8344	1.830	9.220	12.861	4.288	3.419	6.294	1.047
Minimum	3.400	1.230	2.534	12.061	1.683	1.850	3.915	0.911
Std. Dev.	0.466	0.163	2.018	0.272	0.694	0.341	0.628	0.030
Skewness	-0.490	1.628	-0.580	0.451	0.881	-0.775	0.900	0.703
Kurtosis	1.896	4.564	2.181	1.616	2.862	3.626	2.689	3.677
Jarque Bera	3.362	15.237	3.276	4.501	5.082	3.150	5.423	3.966
Probability	0.188	0.0004	0.194	0.105	0.079	0.0207	0.066	0.138
Sum	155.94	39.409	258.86	485.98	104.26	75.54	187.7	37.08
Sum sq Dev	7.8351	0.7222	154.856	2.135	18.353	3.041	14.98	0.034
Observation	37	28	39	38	38	27	39	39

Source: Authors' compilation, 2024

5.2 Unit root test

From Table 5 real exchange rate (REX), unemployment (UNEM), food security (FS), and per capita income (Y) are integrated of order one I(1), which indicates that the variables are I(1) using Augmented Dickey-Fuller test. With regards to the population growth rate (POP), inflation (INF), food import (FIM), and the bioeconomy (BIOE)) the unit root test reveals that these variables are integrated of order zero. Philips-Perron test also reveals food security (FS), unemployment (UNEM), per capita income (Y), and real exchange rate (REX), are integrated of order one which indicates that the variables are I(1) and population growth rate (POP), inflation rate (INF, bioeconomy (BIOE), and food import (FIM) are integrated of order zero that is I(0).

Table 5: Unit Test Result

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test				Philips-Perron (P5.P) Test		
Variable	Level	1st Difference	Status	Level	1st Difference	Status
FS	-0.378306 (0.9014)	-4.5920* (0.0009)	I(1)	0.9216 (0.9947)	-10.8130* (0.0000)	I(1)
POP	-3.141642** (0.0320)	-	I(0)	-3.592684** (0.0106)		I(0)
UNEM	-1.3009 (-.2221)	-2.8321*** (0.0678)	I(1)	-0.3502 (0.9044)	-2.8824**	I(1)
Y	-0.250022 (0.9228)	-4.9235* (0.0003)	I(1)	-0.5898 (0.08609)	-4.9207* (0.0003)	I(1)
FIM	-2.8355*** (0.0704)	-	I(0)	-2.8355*** (0.0704)		I(0)
INF	-3.4551* (0.0150)		I(0)	-3.3382** (0.020)		I(0)
REX	-2.033669 (0.2718)	-4.664120* (0.0006)	I(1)	-2.1923 (0.2122)	-4.5283* (0.0009)	I(1)
BIOE	-2.7120*** (0.0813)		I(0)	-2.8203*** (0.0649)		I(0)

Note * = 1%, ** = 5% and *** = 10% significant level. For the augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test, the automatic maximum lag length based on the Schwarz information criterion is applied while for the Philips-Perron (PP) test, the automatic maximum lag length based on Newey - West Banswidth is applied.

5.4 GMM Result of Bioeconomy on Food Security in Nigeria

Table 6 below presents the GMM estimates of the effect of bioeconomy on food security in Nigeria. Results from Table 7 show that bioeconomy (BIOE) has a positive and insignificant effect ($t = 2.089$, $p > 0.05$) on food security. This shows that an increase in bioeconomy did not significantly enhance food security. This supports the a priori expectation that an increase in the level of bioeconomy improves food security. This explains that an increase in government investment in bioeconomy sectors primarily the agricultural sector enhances food security. This agrees with the view that bioeconomy through biotechnology processes helps in improving the existing crops available for consumption thereby enhancing food security. This also supports studies by Sharad, Jaya and Jha (2010) and Oguntuase (2018) which state that the bioeconomy enhances food security. However, the insignificant effect of bioeconomy on food security could be attributed to the profit-driven attitude of investors of agricultural biotechnology innovations rather than need-driven (Busch et al 1990). These technologies are a response to biotechnology corporations' desire to increase farmers' reliance on seeds that are protected by "intellectual property rights," which are in direct opposition to farmers' long-standing rights to distribute, reproduce, and store seeds (Hobbelink, 1991). The legal rights over seeds are granted to genetic engineers by the emergence of genetic technologies. Although biotechnology has potential applications that could eventually lessen the environmental burden of hazardous agricultural chemicals, other uses could prolong the pesticide era and encourage additional financial investment in pesticide manufacturing (Doyle, 1988). Given that the same food utilized for human consumption is also used to provide fuel (bioenergy), the bioeconomy's little impact on Nigeria's food security may be related to competition for food fuel.

Likewise, food import (FIM) has a positive and significant effect on food security ($t = 3.002$, $p < 0.05$). This shows that a proportionate increase in food importation spurs food security. Per capita income (Y) has a positive but insignificant effect on food security ($t = 0.689$, $p > 0.05$) in Nigeria. This indicates that an increase in per capita income does not significantly promote food security. The unemployment rate (UNEM) negatively and significantly affects food security ($t = -2.497$, $p < 0.05$) in Nigeria. This shows that an increase in unemployment impedes the achievement of sustainable development. However, the results from Table 7 show that the effect of the population growth rate (POP) on food security is negative but statistically insignificant ($t = -0.854$, $p > 0.05$). This indicates an increase in population impedes food security. This indicates that the level of sustainable development reduces as the population growth rate increases. The study also shows that the real exchange rate (REX) has a negative and insignificant effect ($t = -1.876$, $p > 0.05$) on food security. This implies that a high exchange rate does not promote food security. The results further indicate that inflation (INF) has a negative but insignificant effect ($t = -1.107$, $p > 0.05$) on sustainable

development. This shows that a higher inflation rate affects the living standard of the citizens which further hinders the attainment of sustainable development.

The lagged value of food security has a negative and insignificant effect ($t = -0.251$, $p > 0.05$) on food security, which implies that achieving sustainable development in the previous year did not translate to sustainable development in the current year. From Table 6 post-estimation tests were carried out to test for the validity of the instruments used in the model. The Sargan test value is 0.632, which is closer to one. This demonstrates the validity of the instrumental variables' moment condition. This demonstrates that the model's variables are suitable and unrelated to the error term. Both AR (1) and AR (2), which have probability values of 0.628 and 0.365, respectively, show that there is no autocorrelation in the model when the Arellano-Bond test is performed.

Table 6: GMM Estimate on The Effect of Bioeconomy on food security in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: Food Security		
Independent Variables	Co-efficient	P-value
FS (1)	-0.1350 (-0.2514)	[0.8098]
POP	-5.347 (-0.853)	[0.4606]
FIM	0.0876 (3.002)	[0.0400]**
LBIOE	0.091 (2.089)	[0.0821]***
UNEM	-1.2770 (-2.497)	[0.0467]**
INF	-0.0689 (-1.1068)	[0.3107]
Y	0.7758 (0.689)	[0.5168]
REX	-0.0578 (-1.876)	[0.1097]
Instrument rank =13		
Sargan Test	= 0.632	
AR (1)	= 0.628	
AR (2)	= 0.365	

Note: 1. * =1%, ** = 5%, ***=10%
 2. () are *t*- statistics
 3. [] are p values
 3. Source: Authors' computation, 2024.

5.5 Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

As populations grow and the demand for food increases, it is critical to invest in sustainable food systems that can support economic growth while minimizing environmental impact. Ensuring equitable access to nutritious food is not only a moral imperative but also a key driver of economic prosperity and social stability across the world. The study concludes that food security is improved by the bioeconomy. Therefore, the study suggests that to increase the nutritional value of staple crops and ensure that people in the economy have access to food regardless of population growth, farmers who produce the majority of the country's food—should be encouraged to use biofortified seeds that have been approved by the National Biosafety Management Agency. These genetically modified seeds available to farmers in Nigeria include drought-resistant maize, nutrient-enriched cassava, and vitamin A orange sweet potato. The study further concludes that for the government to ensure that bioeconomy through the biotechnological process has a positive and significant effect on food security in Nigeria, there is a need for the government to encourage public-private partnership to overcome the monopolistic ability of private sector innovators. The government should also promote farmers' that is right to save and sell genetically modified seeds to reduce the negative effect the intellectual property rights might have on food security.

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